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Review

Blockchain Based Digital Health Care OBOR Polices Framework

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Abstract: *The OBOR health exchange and cooperation, to fabricate the Health Silk Road. Blockchain technology is advancing toward the healthcare industry, and this is just the start. At this point, most healthcare associations perceive that blockchain could extraordinarily diminish the time, expenses and risk related with how they operate. In this paper, we depict a decentralized individual information the executives framework that guarantees clients possess and control their information. We actualize a convention that transforms a blockchain into a robotized get to control supervisor that does not require trust in an outsider. We will also examine the Blockchain Based Digital HealthCare OBOR Policy Framework which is included at extending health and related people-to-people exchanges, safeguarding health security, promoting health development, strengthening cooperation on health related innovation to improve people's health and well-being, enhancing social cohesion and inclusiveness. At the end we will also discuss the expected outcomes, result and future directions on it.*

Keywords: *One Belt One Road; Sustainable Development Goals; World Health Organization; Blockchain; Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development; Digital Health Care*

1. Introduction

As China executes its “thirteenth 5-year” get ready for national economic and social development, one may ask how endeavors being proposed will influence global health through the alleged Belt and Road Initiative. The Belt and Road Initiative means to associate the Asian–

Pacific Economic Area with the European Economic Area by working up two maritime routes, alluded to as the 21st century Silk Road. Along these lines, in spite of the fact that its essential point identifies with trades, the activity has numerous understood effects on worldwide health, some of which we give experiences into here.

The Belt and Road Initiative also known as One Belt One Road (OBOR) also gives a typical stage to enhance the capacity of taking care of local general wellbeing administrations crises through plague data sharing, trade of preventive and interventional strategies, and preparing wellbeing experts. China has resolved to give therapeutic help and crisis restorative guide to OBOR accomplices, and to do territorial collaboration and coordination in maternal and youngster wellbeing, incapacity recovery, and the board of significant sicknesses, including HIV, tuberculosis, and jungle fever. China consented to increment territorial participation in science and innovation through setting up joint labs or research focuses, universal innovation exchange, and information interpretation focuses [1].

Demonstrated authority is critical to the fate of worldwide health laws. The OBOR Initiative gives a predictable instrument to arrangement, appropriation of aggregate activity, and observing of standardizing rules. It likewise gives a chance to the worldwide north to associate with the worldwide south through this regular stage of economic security, which lines up with numerous objectives of the UN's Sustainable Development Goals. [3].

To additionally deepen and innovate on The OBOR health exchange and cooperation, to fabricate the Health Silk Road and to drive forward the shared improvement of significant nations' health service, and to actualize health related agreement in the Joint Communiqué of The OBOR International Cooperation Forum Roundtable Summit, Health Ministers and senior authorities from the health sector in China and other taking part nations, and in addition agents from World Health Organization (WHO), The Joint United Nations Program on HIV/AIDS (UNAIDS), Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), Global Alliance for Vaccines and Immunization (GAVI), and Global Fund attended the Belt and Road High Level Meeting on Health Cooperation towards Health Silk Road in Beijing, China on August 18th 2017 [4,5].

The rest of the paper is organized as follows. Section II talks about the state of art of existing literature on underlying study area. In section III, the proposed Blockchain Based Digital

HealthCare OBOR Polices Framework. In section IV Expected output and result has been discussed. Finally, the paper ends with a short conclusion and Future work in section V.

2. Background and Related work

Reviewing that China has built up a strong establishment of cooperation between the applicable Belt and Road countries, reciprocal participation has gained incredible progress and shaped solid relations of common interests and significant kinship.

Perceiving that exchange and participation in health is a critical segment of The Belt and Road Initiative and play an imperative part in the improvement of relations amongst China and Belt and Road related countries, enhancing reciprocal and multilateral cooperation, extending the friendship between people and constructing a closer community of common destiny [2].

We recognize that health is the core of development, an essential and result of improvement, and a compelling file in the estimation of sustainable development. The improvement and upkeep of the essentialness of Belt and Road nations' national health frameworks and pushing forward the health cooperation amongst Belt and Road nations isn't just helpful for enhancing individuals' health, yet will likewise add to advancing economic development.

We perceive that doing all-round, multi-level and exclusive requirement research in medicinal science and innovation can extraordinarily promote the development and interpretation of medical research. We likewise resolve to cooperate to build up The Belt and Road Health Policy Research Network and to accomplish the health related objectives in the United Nations 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development (SDGs). Strengthening medical science and technology development and health industry cooperation will help to meet the multi-level, diversified needs in health, and improve national health quality [6,7,8,].

There are not many industries that shouldn't be either excited or worried about the potential, use cases, proof of- concepts, and full-fledged businesses models based on blockchain technology emerging at an increasing pace. One of the strong feature of the blockchain is its decentralized nature, allowing permitted parties not to pay intermediaries (Middlemen), thus saving time and avoiding conflicts.

In 1994, Nick Szabo, a lawful researcher, and cryptographer, understood that the decentralized record could be utilized for savvy contracts, generally called self-executing contracts, blockchain contracts, or advanced contracts. In this configuration, contracts could be changed over to PC code, put away and repeated on the framework and administered by the system of PCs that run

the blockchain. This would likewise result in record input coming about into computerized tutor structure empowering exchanging of cash and provisioning of administrations and so on. [9]. A decentralized autonomous organization, or just DAO, is a business or association whose choices are made electronically by a composed PC code or through the vote of its individuals. Basically it is an arrangement of hard coded guidelines that characterize which moves an association will make. Blockchain has been received by UAE government with the point of 10x savvy Dubai. The vision of 10X smart Dubai is to reduce/eliminate the human intervention in jobs and develop such autonomous organizations [12]. Please see Figure 1 for Vision of 10x smart Dubai.

Figure 1. “10x Smart Dubai

Digital Healthcare, remote consultations, and the growing desire of consumers to seek out the best possible value no matter where that care is centered have made it more common for providers and consumers to collaborate across health systems. Close collaboration between payers and providers is a fundamental requirement for value-based care, yet many entities struggle to break down their data siloes and exchange information in a secure and timely manner. We believe Blockchain may be able to help organizations leap over these hurdles while keeping the patient at the center of the Healthcare Eco-system. [10, 11].

2.1 Pakistan’s digital healthcare system and services

2.1.1 E-IIaj

Khyber Pakhtunkhwa(KPK) Launches First Online Healthcare Facility In The Province, E-IIaj As per Tribune, the experimental project was introduced in Bilahi area of district Mansehra. It was

in collaboration with K-P Information Technology Board. The aim of this project to reduce the burden on tertiary health care hospitals. As per Shahram Khan Tarakai, the health minister, this project will be further extended to more districts in future. The reason for launching this project as per few officials is that the government was not able to post specialized, experienced doctors at each and every health unit in KPK. Tarakai said that many people had to travel all the way from their hilly area to the commercial areas in search of specialized doctors and better health facilities. High-speed internet connectivity will be used to connect experienced doctors with these centers. Staff will be assigned positions in the center to help patients connect with the doctors in Peshawar. Through video call patient can connect. Tarakai informed, “This center will offer services for patients with cardiac problems, mother and child health, skin, and ENT besides other issues on the spot where five specialized doctors will be offer services under one roof.” [14]

2.1.2 e-Cards (Health)

NADRA (National Database and Registration Authority) facilitates in providing e-card solutions with cash disbursement, data verification and approval management provisioning data identification, storage and verification of identities. Health cards provide better treatment facilities with digitized data ensuring paperless environment; Providing streamlined administrative processes to hospitals and insurance companies with reduced participant misuse of resources. Doctors have access to the database and the cards have data encryption. The secure and readily available history of patients ensures high quality of medication and care services. Prime Minister National Health Program landed in Pakistan is providing all required facilities to the deserving citizens of the country [15].

Fig. 2. Health care system

2.2 China digital healthcare system and services current state-of-the-art

In 2014, approximately \$700 million in venture funding poured into digital health care in China, with investors supporting all things digital, from e-commerce to online physician-and-patient communication services to disease management apps. This is just the beginning.

As mobile and Internet-based technologies are developed and deployed to improve health care delivery for China's population of 1.3 billion people, the nation's digital health-care market will grow exponentially. We expect that this market (measured by spending on digital health care) will expand from \$3 billion in 2014 to \$110 billion in 2020.

Regardless of the dynamics within any particular segment, all players must develop new mind-sets and new business models: Digital players, Pharmaceutical and medtech companies, Drug distributors and retailers, Payers, Companies [16].

2.2.1 Digital Health Care Takes Off

Three trends are driving the digital health-care revolution in China.

The first is the widespread adoption of new technologies such as mobile devices, cloud computing, and big-data analytics. In 2014, for example, almost 40 percent of people in China had a smartphone and used the device for three hours a day (on average). Combine that with the increasing availability of high-speed Internet access and big data, and companies will have the ability to offer digital solutions—everything from remote patient monitoring to drug purchasing using smartphones—to large swaths of the population in China.

The second is the continuing effort by the Chinese government to address long-standing inefficiencies and unmet needs within the health care system—an effort that digital health care will help to advance. Remote physician consultation and online appointment booking, for example, can help mitigate the overutilization of large hospitals—and the underutilization of smaller facilities—in China; many patients still flock to large facilities for basic needs like renewing a prescription. And new solutions that allow continual communication between physicians and patients will deliver much-needed improvements in patient care over the long term.

The third trend is an increasingly favorable regulatory environment. Following a \$9.5 billion investment by the Ministry of Health (now the National Health and Family Planning Commission) in 2012 to develop electronic medical records (EMRs) and improve hospital

information systems, the Chinese government has intensified its efforts to boost digital health care. For example, the government reduced barriers in e-commerce, making it easier to register online pharmacies, and is expected to allow certain prescription drugs to be sold online sometime in 2016. In addition, the government has allowed hospitals in some provinces to run pilots involving remote diagnosis and medication prescription.

2.2.2 The Landscape Today—and in the Future

As trends encouraging digital health care gather momentum, new business models are emerging, within both the health-care service and e-commerce spaces. New digital entrants, including large, established companies as well as new venture players, are driving much of this effort as they stake out territory in health care and move to shape the digital health-care market.

For example, the search engine company Baidu is leveraging its core search business to offer health information to consumers and link consumers to online appointment booking and remote consultations. Baidu also now sells smart wearable devices through its Dulife brand. In partnership with the Beijing government, Baidu is using the devices to track and analyze health information; the aim is to improve health service delivery in the city.

Alibaba Group, meanwhile, has expanded its e-commerce platform to include online pharmacies and is developing an app that would leverage the company's Alipay online-payment system to allow patients to fill prescriptions online. The company is also building a new service platform that will enable physicians to remotely diagnose and treat patients. And its "future hospital" initiative will allow hospitals to digitize their patient-services processes.

Social-media player Tencent is extending the reach of its Wechat social and payment platform into health care. The company rolled out Intelligent Health, an IT platform to provide hospitals with services such as online and mobile appointment booking and payments, in 2014. Tencent is also investing in companies to create a full suite of services for patients and physicians across the value chain. Among these investments is a stake in Dingxiangyuan, an online network for China's health-care professionals.

At the same time, many venture-backed new players, among them Chunyu and Xingren Doctor, are developing offerings such as remote physician-consultation services. Traditional insurer Ping An Insurance, meanwhile, launched an app called Ping An Good Doctor, which, among other things, allows remote physician consultation. And some traditional pharmaceutical distributors

and retailers, such as Shanghai Pharmaceuticals, are actively exploring e-commerce opportunities.

With increasing numbers of new entrants and investment, the momentum in digital health care is undeniable. Of the \$110 billion in digital health-care spending that we project in China in 2020, health care services will account for the bulk of the market at \$95 billion, and e-commerce will contribute approximately \$15 billion.

A good portion of this growth will come from the redirection of existing spending in the off-line world to digital services. But the increase also reflects the development of entirely new businesses and revenue streams. Growth will be spread across digital health-care service segments, with the largest absolute increases in revenues concentrated in the already booming disease-management and physician-patient-communication segments.

Regardless of whether the changes in health care a major threat or a tantalizing new opportunity are, companies must respond now. In the digital age, inaction will lead to failure [17].

3. How Can Blockchain Be Applied to Health Care?

One of the first use cases that typically pops up when discussing blockchain and health care is data exchange. Take medication prescribing as an example. A patient's medications are frequently prescribed and filled by different entities — hospitals, provider offices, pharmacies, etc. Each one maintains its own “source of truth” of medications for a patient, frequently with outdated or simply wrong information. As a result, providers in different networks, or on different EHRs, may not see one another's prescriptions. Additionally, electronic prescriptions must be directed to specific pharmacies, and paper prescriptions can be duplicated or lost [18].

3.1 Clinical data sharing. Advance directives, genetic studies, allergies, problem lists, imaging studies, and pathology reports are just some of the data elements that could be distributed. Alternately, instead of storing actual patient data, blockchain could be used to store access controls — like who a patient has authorized to see their health data — even if the clinical data itself is stored by the EHR.

- 3.2 **Public health.** A shared, immutable stream of de-identified patient information could more readily identify pandemics, independent of governmental bodies currently aggregating this data — for example, an influenza reporting system.
- 3.3 **Research and clinical trials.** Distributing patient consent or trial results could foster data sharing, audit trials, and clinical safety analyses.
- 3.4 **Administrative and financial information.** Insurance eligibility and claims processing workflows could benefit from blockchain and have decreased transactional costs.
- 3.5 **Patient and provider identity.** National (or international) patient or provider identities could be secured in the blockchain, providing the basis for health data portability and security.
- 3.6 **Patient-generated data.** Personal health devices, “wearables,” “Internet of Things” (IOT) devices, and patient-reported outcomes are just some examples of patient-generated data that could leverage the blockchain for security and sharing.

Most of these use cases are top-down: data used and generated on behalf of patients. But perhaps the greatest potential of blockchain technology is the empowering of patients to own and gather their own data. In many ways, the promise of blockchain lies outside the current health information technology framework — directly challenging the siloed, centralized data stores that dominate health care data today.

4. Blockchain Based Digital HealthCare OBOR Polices Framework Strategy and Business Model

In this paper we will look at extending health and related people-to-people exchanges, safeguarding health security, promoting health development, strengthening cooperation on health-related innovation to improve people's health and well-being, enhancing social cohesion and inclusiveness. Cooperate to set up The Belt and Road Health Policy Research Network and accomplish the health-related goals in the United Nations 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development. Push forward the Belt and Road countries in the observing, counteractive action and control, and reaction to major infectious diseases, in the coordination and collaboration in general health crisis reaction, and in fortifying the center capacities as required in "international Health Regulations (2005)" and in the foundation of Belt and Road Public Health Cooperation Network in order to mutually address the difficulties. Strengthen the interaction of health human resources. Attach importance to the exchange of personnel, through the exchange of health and

medical experts, organizing various health professional and technical training courses and seminars to enhance the exchange of experience and personnel training.

The important pace of globalization has increased the cross-cutting nature of health threats and demonstrated the shared benefits of universal access to quality care: Expanding cooperation in health under the framework of the Belt and Road Initiative, strengthening information sharing/services, International health cooperation aims to improve public health and Implementation strategies for developing and implementing PCIC-based service delivery.

4.1 Proposed Strategy: Introduce E Card and Video Call health service on OBOR

CallHealth provides doctor consultation (through a video conference), diagnostic tests, professional home care services like nursing, physiotherapy and a family doctor at patient’s home, beside home-delivering prescribed medicines, and facilitating transportation in the case of advanced tests and hospitalization. In the OBOR we launch this service in the reset area if any person need first aid then first aid person calls doctors and they explain what is happen with him/her. On the time patients received good quality services.We can introduce E card payment on OBOR same like Pakistani services. This will also be very convenient for every patients.

4.2 Proposed Framework

With the help of cited literature, we have proposed a theoretical framework i-e Blockchain Based Digital HealthCare OBOR Polices Framework shown in Figure 3.1.

Figure 3. “Blockchain Based Digital HealthCare OBOR Polices Framework OBOR”

We are purposing a digital health platform to all stakeholders of OBOR. This platform will be developed as per defined and developed strategies and polices regarding health related that are already stated in SDG3 and based on SDG3 and China 2030 agenda for implementation of all SDG policies we are proposing a digital channel that will be easily accessible to all stakeholders over OBOR and as Blockchain is a secure, immutable and shared ledger technology and currently whole world is focusing on the implementation of Blockchain technology because of it's security and provenance. As we already discussed that UAE government already moved on Dubai smart 10x. This blockchain based digital healthcare proposed framework will help Government of China to achieve SDG-3.

4.3 Proposed Business Model

Team or Company Name: Blockchain Based Digital HealthCare OBOR Polices		Date: 07/11/18	☒ Primary Canvas ☐ Alternative Canvas	
Key Partners Who are our Key Partners? Who are our Key Suppliers? Which Key Resources are we acquiring from partners? Which Key Activities do partners perform?	Key Activities What Key Activities do our Value Propositions require? Our Distribution Channels? Customer Relationships? Revenue streams?	Value Proposition What value do we deliver to the customer? Which one of our customer's problems are we helping to solve? What bundles of products and services are we offering to each Customer Segment? Which customer needs are we satisfying?	Customer Relationships What type of relationship does each of our Customer Segments expect us to establish and maintain with them? Which ones have we established? How are they integrated with the rest of our business model? How costly are they?	Customer Segments For whom are we creating value? Who are our most important customers?
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> OBOR, Government of China Government Policy and Strategic Departments, Hospitals and IT experts Policy and Procedure Development Manager, Blockchain Architecture and Development Experts, Hospital staff for testing of Implemented Digital System To develop Strategy for Blockchain based Digital Healthcare system OBOR polices 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develop Strategy and policy for OBOR healthcare system and Build Blockchain Based Tool for digital, safe and secure Healthcare system Hospitals, Insurance Companies, Pharma Companies and IT Companies. 24x7 service Digital platform, Application will be used and generate revenue on the basis of traffic on digital healthcare system. Government of China will also be revenue stream 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> To provide 24x7 Healthcare system on OBOR. To secure life in case of emergency by using this application as alerts will be sent to all distributed ledgers using blockchain technology on timely basis and Doctor will respond to emergency incident as early as he/she can. High availability of secure and safe health care service over OBOR Instant Consultation, Digital Payments, Treatment, Data & 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Provide them secure 24x7 Digital Health services. Formulation of Baseline Strategy and policy document. This document will provide baseline to Technology department for the development of Digital tool. Approximately 50,000 USD 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> OBOR and Government of China OBOR users and patients

	<p><i>Key Resources</i></p> <p>What Key Resources do our Value Propositions require?</p> <p>Our Distribution Channels? Customer Relationships?</p> <p>Revenue Streams?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Strategy and policy makers and Blockchain Developers. • Hospitals, Insurance Companies, Pharma Companies and IT Companies. • Application users who will avail service through this digital Healthcare system 	<p><i>Analytics.</i></p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Patients and people having emergency on OBOR. 	<p><i>Channels</i></p> <p>Through which Channels do our Customer Segments want to be reached? How are we reaching them now? How are our Channels integrated?</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digital HealthCare Blockchain Based Application/ System • Hospital. We will have integrated hospital thorough Blockchain distributed system across the OBOR. 	
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Expected output/Results

In this section expected output of blockchain based digital healthcare OBOR polices framework will be discussed in detail.

5.1 Strengthening Services/Sharing information

5.1.1 Strengthening Services

First, Paradigm shift in disease control by sound epidemiological knowledge, second Progressive control of disease. thirdly,creating a supportive environment for citizen engagement in health promotion and improvement

5.1.2 Sharing information

Communicable diseases, Disease prevention and control, Medical relief and assistance, and Exchanges on traditional medical research

5.2 Aims to improve health delivery system on OBOR

Improve workforce composition and competency for health care service delivery, Flexible health labor market and efficient health workforce management.Increased consultation and exchanges on health policy issues,Building institutions, Defining international health standards and norms, Enhanced cooperation in disease prevention and control, Training and capacity building.

5.3 Blockchain Benefits

How beneficial would it be if you can have the full history of your health? What if all medicines you've taken, information of every doctor's visit, operations, and illness could be captured accurately and efficiently? This is what Blockchain in healthcare industry could do exceedingly well.

With blockchain healthcare applications, the quality of health care is predicted to rise, and the risks and costs are likely to go down. And as you probably know that data stored on blockchains can be shared in real time across a group of people or institutions, so each event or transaction is time-stamped as a permanent record, which cannot be tampered.

On permissionless blockchains, every individual can see all records. Furthermore, on permissioned blockchains, protection can be kept up by an understanding what gatherings can see the assentation, by veiling the personality of the gathering.

In any case, numerous medicinal services associations are moving quick and even appear to have a lead for blockchain in social insurance. As of late, IBM directed a blockchain contemplate where they studied 200 social insurance officials from 16 nations and found that; 16% of them aren't simply testing, yet they hope to assemble business blockchain applications before the finish of 2017. Truth be told, they're driving the accuse of ongoing blockchain applications with which they hope to bring down the erosions keeping them down. They are all around centered around getting to new and confided in data that they can keep secure, safe, and enter new markets also. Be that as it may, in spite of the present happiness, we should comprehend the sensible advantages of blockchain in human services industry [13].

Figure 4. Blockchain Benefits

6. Conclusion and Future Work

The aim of this work is to recommend a strategy for achievement for SDG 3 goal for OBOR China Project. To provide a strategy that will help china government to achieve SDG 3 goal till 2030 and also provide monitoring the overarching health goals. In this paper we proposed that we will achieve SDG 3 at OBOR with collaboration with other countries that will help us to achieve goals by collaboration with other countries and enhance collaboration among international academia R&D activities as well. As this paper also proposed digital services using blockchain based technologies so that our SDG 3 goal will be achieved through advance technologies and will be the baseline standard for rest of the world. For promotion of international collaboration among academia we connected Pakistan Institute of Engineering and Applied Sciences, Islamabad, Pakistan Blochchain research group so that in future we will collaboratively work on this framework and develop such baseline technology that will be used by rest of world toAchieve the SDG-3 Goal on timely basis by applying latest technologies and strengthen the China.

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